

Genetic diversity estimated among rice cultivars using restriction landmark genomic scanning method

M. Kawase, Laboratory of Plant Biotechnology, Crop Improvement Department, Shikoku National Agricultural Experiment Station, 3-1, Sen'yu-cho 1, Zentsuji, Kagawa 765, Japan

The restriction landmark genomic scanning (RLGS) method is a new technique developed for analyzing genomic DNA of higher organisms (Hatada et al 1991). RLGS, which uses restriction enzyme sites as landmarks, requires direct labeling at the restriction sites and two-dimensional electrophoresis to resolve these landmarks. It gives a two-dimensional pattern with thousands of scattered spots after autoradiography. The RLGS method provides unbiased information on genetic polymorphism throughout the whole

genome, an accurate estimation of genetic similarity, and is applicable to rice cultivars (Kawase 1994).

We extracted DNA from leaves of 14-d-old seedlings of two Japanese improved cultivars (Nipponbare and Koshihikari) and a Chinese land race (Liu' Zhou' Bao' Ya' Zao)' (Kawase 1994). RLGS was conducted based on the procedure described by Hatada et al (1991), which consisted of blocking reaction, landmark cleavage, labeling, first fractionation, and second fractionation. Genetic similarities between cultivars were calculated using the measure devised by Dice (1945), which was suggested for DNA polymorphism by Nei and Li (1979):

$$GS(i,j) = 2N(i,j)/[N(i)+N(j)],$$

where $GS(i,j)$ = the measure of genetic similarity between cultivars i and j ; $N(i,j)$ = the total spots common to i and j ; and $N(i)$ and $N(j)$ = the number of spots for cultivars i and j , respectively.

More than 3,000 landmarks were detected as scattered spots on the auto-

radiogram (Fig. 1). The relative position and the intensity of each spot were highly reproducible. An RLGS profile was unique to each cultivar used.

The RLGS profiles of Nipponbare and Liu' Zhou' Bao' Ya' Zao showed quite different patterns, indicating a wide genetic difference between the two cultivars. Restriction fragment length polymorphism analysis also revealed that they were distantly related (Kawase et al 1991). A limited area (Fig. 1) could be compared, although the different patterns made it rather difficult to identify each spot. Nipponbare and Liu' Zhou' Bao' Ya' Zao have 387 and 403 spots in the area, respectively, of which 136 were scored as common or indistinguishable spots. The low GS value, calculated as 0.344, suggests large genetic diversity among rice cultivars.

Nipponbare and Koshihikari showed similar patterns. An area showing the clearest resolution contained 1,156 spots common to both cultivars (Fig. 2).

1. More than 3,000 spots were scattered on the RLGS profile obtained by autoradiography (Kawase 1994). Nipponbare (a) and Liu'Zhou'Bao'Ya'Zao (b) showed quite different patterns. The enclosed area was used for estimating the GS value between the two cultivars.

2. RLGS profiles of Nipponbare and Koshihikari were highly similar. However, the cultivars were distinguished based on the presence and absence of particular spots in the enclosed area (Kawase 1994). Arrow heads indicate the spots unique to each of the two cultivars compared.

Additionally, 24 and 25 spots were found unique to Nipponbare and Koshihikari, respectively. The GS value was calculated as 0.980.

The RLGS method can be a powerful fingerprinting technique for estimating genetic diversity in rice as well as for identifying cultivars.

Cited references

- Dice LR. 1945. Measures of the amount of ecologic association between species. *Ecology* 26:297-302.
- Hatada I, Hayashizaki Y, Hirotsune S, Komatsubara H, Mukai T. 1991. A genomic scanning method for higher organisms using restriction sites as landmarks. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 88:9523-9527.
- Kawase M, Kishimoto N, Tanaka T, Yoshimura A, Yoshimura S, Saito K, Saito A, Yano M,

- Takeda N, Nagamine T, Nakagahra M. 1991. Intraspecific variation and genetic differentiation based on restriction fragment length polymorphism in Asian cultivated rice, *Oryza sativa* L. *Rice genetics II*. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute. p 467-473.
- Nei M, Li WH. 1979. Mathematical model for studying genetic variation in terms of restriction endonucleases. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 76:5269-5273. ■

Character expression of a rice dwarf mutant with lax panicle

Y. Futsuhara, T. Horio, and S. Tanaka, Faculty of Agriculture, Meijo University, Tenpaku, Nagoya 468, Japan; and J. Yonemaru, Tohoku National Agricultural Experiment Station, Morioka, 020-01, Japan

A dwarf mutant with lax panicle was induced from the parent cultivar Fujiminori by 200 Gy of X-ray irradiation. The mutant exhibits leaf rolling during the early vegetative phase until the appearance of the 6th or 7th leaf. Inheritance of this mutant trait

was studied from an F₂ segregation involving a cross between the dwarf mutant and the parent cultivar. The F₁ was normal and the F₂ segregated into 103 normal plants and 39 dwarf plants, giving a good fit to a 3:1 ratio ($\chi^2 = 0.460$, $P = 0.498$). Pleiotropic action of the dwarf mutant gene appears to be responsible for the lax panicles and rolled leaves. Panicle density is a complex character, which consists of many component characters such as spikelet number, panicle length, and number of branches (Futsuhara et al 1979). Panicle laxness in this mutant could be attributed to the decrease in total spikelets and branches, especially secondary branches (see table).

Rolled leaf is a marker trait that can be used in selecting dwarf mutant types during juvenile stage.

To determine the annual and seasonal variations in various agronomic traits, the dwarf mutant and its parent cultivar were tested in 1992 and 1994. The rice plants were raised under two seeding times (early and late seedings) only in 1994.

The dwarf mutant showed different responses to various seeding conditions (see table). The difference in panicle density between parent and mutant grown under late seeding condition was not significant. Seed fertility of the mutant, which was significantly less than that of the parent